

Incorporating Pineapple Leaf Fiber into Meitei Traditional Textiles: A Cultural and Sustainable Perspective

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Abstract:

This study explores the application of pineapple leaf fiber (PALF) yarns for traditional Meitei textiles, focusing on Rani Phi and Muga Phaneke garments. PALF was used to replace conventional materials, aiming to enhance sustainability and preserve cultural heritage. Fabric samples were produced in manageable sizes—for Rani Phi and Muga Phaneke. Rani Phi featured a union plain weave with extra weft rayon yarns (242D), traditional motifs, and a color scheme of undyed white warp (silk-50's with Z twist) and creamy weft (PALF yarn-30's with Z twist) with red ornamentation. The fabric demonstrated a GSM of 56 g/m², a thickness of 0.24 mm, and sufficient tensile strength. Muga Phaneke, utilizing a plain weave with extra weft polyester yarns, exhibited an orange warp (Polyester yarn-18's with Z twist), natural weft (PALF yarn- 8's with Z twist), and red motifs, achieving a GSM of 184.4 g/m², a thickness of 0.57 mm, and higher tensile strength than Rani Phi. Consumer feedback from 74 Meitei weavers showed strong acceptance of PALF textiles, appreciating their silk-like appearance, natural color, and cultural motifs, with high commercial potential indicated. The findings validate PALF as a viable, sustainable alternative for traditional Meitei textiles, preserving authenticity while enhancing production and market feasibility.

Keywords: Meitei community, Muga Phaneke, PALF, Rani phi, Sustainability, Traditional motifs

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1. Introduction

India benefits from a rich variety of natural fibers, including cotton, jute, bamboo, sisal, coir, abaca, kenaf, banana, and ramie, which are plentiful across its diverse regions. These fibers possess distinct characteristics influenced by their plant origin, species, and geographic locations. A substantial portion, approximately 30-40%, of agricultural and forest waste is often burned or left to decompose, leading to serious environmental issues. Addressing this problem involves finding valuable uses for these waste materials, which can enhance the economic viability of their cultivation and create employment opportunities. [1, 2]

Cellulose fibers, derived from leaves, stalks, or pseudo stems, hold significant economic value, supporting the livelihoods and food security of many farmers and processors. Innovations in extraction techniques ensure a consistent year-round supply of these plant fibers, promoting value addition in textiles and the diversification of products. Furthermore, initiatives for extracting plant fibers contribute to poverty reduction and job creation in rural and semi-urban regions. [3]

In the 21st century, clothing plays a pivotal role, influencing every facet of our lives. It transcends mere fashion to serve as a cultural mirror, reflecting societal values, aspirations, and

concerns about our world. The clothing industry is in constant flux, with trends rapidly emerging and fading. Despite this volatility, there is an increasing awareness of the environmental and social implications of clothing. The drive towards sustainability has gained prominence within and beyond the industry, highlighting the urgent need to reevaluate clothing production—from raw material sourcing to the ethical treatment of workers.

Traditional textiles, which had been eclipsed by synthetic materials due to the latter's efficiency and lower costs, are making a notable comeback. Their enduring appeal and typically more environmentally friendly production methods make them attractive to designers and consumers. [4] Fabrics like cotton, linen, wool, and silk are regaining popularity not only for their aesthetic qualities but also for their sustainable attributes. Ultimately, the emphasis on sustainability in fashion represents a fundamental shift towards a more responsible and equitable industry, rather than just a passing trend. [5]

Northeast India is a region of stunning natural beauty, characterized by lush landscapes, rolling hills, dense forests, and diverse wildlife. Rich in natural resources, including flora, fauna, and mineral deposits, it also boasts vibrant cultures and traditions, with each state offering unique customs, languages, and festivals [6]. Agriculture and handloom weaving play a crucial role in the socio-economic fabric of states like Manipur and others in the Northeast. These sectors provide essential livelihoods, while also preserving cultural heritage and traditional craftsmanship.

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Pineapple cultivation (*Ananas comosus*) is a vital agricultural activity in Northeast India, particularly in Manipur, one of the seven sister states. Locally referred to as "Kihom," the pineapple plant significantly influences the region's agricultural economy. Data from the Imphal Free Press (2023) indicate that Manipur produced an impressive 134.82 metric tons of pineapples during the 2021-2022 harvest season, making it the sixth largest producer in India.

However, despite the high fruit yield, there is a notable underutilization of pineapple resources in Manipur. While the fruit is harvested for consumption and commercial use, the leaves are typically discarded post-harvest. This represents a missed opportunity to fully exploit the pineapple plant's potential, thereby missing out on additional economic and environmental benefits that could be gained from utilizing the leaves.

Pineapple Leaf Fiber (PALF) offers many advantages as an alternative fiber. It shares similar qualities with silk, such as long, fine fibers and a shiny appearance, making it well-suited for various textile uses, [7, 8] including the traditional weaving methods in Manipur. By using PALF in these textiles, weavers can create fabrics that look like silk but are much cheaper, making them more affordable and accessible to a wider range of people. Utilization of the local pineapple leaves for making fiber for textile is needed to fulfill the waste management.

This study aims to explore the incorporation of Pineapple Leaf Fiber (PALF) into Meitei traditional textiles from both cultural and sustainable perspectives. By integrating PALF, which shares similar properties with silk but is more cost-effective and eco-friendly, the research seeks to enhance the accessibility and appeal of traditional Meitei textiles. The objective is to assess how PALF can contribute to preserving cultural heritage while promoting sustainability in textile production, offering an alternative to conventional fibers that can benefit weavers, consumers, and the environment. The selected traditional textiles for the study were Rani phi and Muga phanek worn by women of Meitei community during festivals and occasions.

2. Methodology

The extraction of pineapple fibers began with raw materials sourced from local pineapple growers. The process involved both manual hand extraction and mechanical extraction methods, complemented by a water retting procedure lasting 5-7 days, depending on weather conditions [11]. Mechanical extraction was conducted at the CSIR-NEIST branch laboratory in Lamphel, Manipur, ensuring standardized conditions. Following extraction, the fibers underwent thorough washing and scouring to remove any residual impurities [12]. The scouring process was performed using 2g of commercial detergent per liter of water and 2g of sodium carbonate (soda ash) per liter of water, with a material-to-liquor ratio of 1:40. The solution was heated to

60°C and maintained for 45 minutes. After scouring, the material was thoroughly washed with water. The cleaned fibers were then carefully dried, completing the preparation process for further experimentation and use. This systematic approach ensured the production of high-quality pineapple leaf fibers [13]. The yield percentage of the fiber from each leaf was 3-4%.

To create a fabric resemblance of traditional Rani-Phi (draped upper garment), an innovative approach was adopted involving the integration of modern materials. The process entailed weaving silk threads into the warp, providing a durable and lustrous foundation, while incorporating pineapple yarn into the weft, introducing a unique texture and sustainable element. This method allows for a contemporary interpretation of the Rani-Phi fabric, blending time-honored craftsmanship with the local fibers.

Figure 1: Extracted pineapple leaf fiber

2.1 Construction of the traditional textiles

To preserve the authenticity of the original Rani-Phi textile, traditional motifs and colors were incorporated into the fabric design. The motifs and colors were meticulously gathered from primary and secondary sources to imbue the fabric with the rich cultural heritage of Manipur. The warps yarns were selected based on the existing warp yarns of the Meitei women's traditional textiles. Using the extra weft technique, the traditional patterns - temple stoops, rice puff motifs, floral motifs, and squirrel motifs were intricately woven into the fabric, demonstrating the weaver's skill and attention to detail. The silk yarn used in the warp, with a denier of 106D (comparable to a 50's count), provides the fabric with originality of the warp yarn. Meanwhile, the weft features developed yarn made from pineapple fiber with a denier of 177D (equivalent to a 30's count), adding a distinctive texture and enhancing the fabric's aesthetic appeal.

Before spinning with the motorized charkha, the ends of the combed Pineapple fiber strands were joined to form a continuous length, ensuring a smoother and uninterrupted spinning process [14, 15]. The pineapple yarn was prepared by using a motorized charkha based on phoenix charkha developed by the researcher. A throw shuttle loom with two

shafts was used to weave the sample. This traditional weaving loom operates by manually throwing the shuttle, which carries the weft yarn, across the shed—the opening created by the raised and lowered warp yarns.

Figure 2 : Weaving of Silk/Pineapple fabric

Figure 3: Weaving of Polyester/Pineapple fabric

To replicate the traditional Muga Phanek (wrapped around lower garment) textile of Manipur, traditionally woven from local mulberry silk by Khurkhul weavers, a new fabric was developed. This was accomplished by combining polyester yarn (295D equivalent to 18's count) in the warp and pineapple yarn (177D) in the weft. This combination, was selected to mimic the texture of the original Muga Phanek while making it more accessible and affordable. Lower denier pineapple yarn was chosen to approximate the thickness of the authentic Muga Phanek. Temple stoops motifs, characteristic of the traditional Muga Phanek borders, were integrated into the fabric design. Additionally, traditional colors were used to ensure the fabric closely mirrored the appearance and cultural significance of the original textile.

2.2 Testing of the constructed textiles

The developed fabrics underwent a series of comprehensive tests to assess their physical properties, adhering to ASTM standards. Tensile strength and elongation were evaluated

according to ASTM Test Method D5035, while the fabric's weight in grams per square meter (GSM) was measured using ASTM Test Method D3776-96. Fabric count was determined through ASTM D3775-98, and fabric thickness was assessed using a compress meter thickness tester as per ASTM Test Method D1777-96. Stiffness was tested using Shirley's stiffness tester following ASTM D1388-18, and the drape coefficient was measured with a drapemeter. [17]

2.3 Feedback from the consumer

An evaluation was performed to explore the potential of using the newly developed pineapple yarn as a substitute for conventional materials in textile weaving. This involved comparing traditional textiles woven with pineapple yarn against the silk textiles traditionally made in Manipur, focusing on their physical characteristics. Additionally, feedback was collected from both Meitei consumers and weavers aged 18 to 60. This feedback addressed various aspects, including aesthetics, cultural significance, and practical considerations related to production and usage.

3. Results and Discussion:

The produced yarns were fine, lustrous, even, and stiff, making them well-suited for crafting traditional textiles of Manipur. The fine texture required for these textiles was achieved through the use of finely twisted yarns, resulting in fabrics with good tensile strength and low elongation. The potential for using very fine 100% pineapple leaf fiber yarn with a Z twist for the Rani phi, and a higher count yarn with the same Z twist for phanek, was evaluated and found feasible. These yarns demonstrated adequate strength and durability for traditional textiles without needing any additional treatment, streamlining the production process, reducing costs, and preserving the authenticity of the textiles.

The plain weave union fabrics, incorporating silk/pineapple and Polyester/pineapple with extra weft traditional motifs and colors, successfully took the essence of Rani phee, muga and muga phanek, respectively. Rani-Phi is a vital component of the traditional attire worn by Meitei women. The name is derived from its creator, Chungkham Rani. Rani phi

The fabric sample created for the traditional Rani Phi/phee, a treasured textile among Meitei women in Manipur, were designed to capture its essence and importance, especially for special occasions such as weddings [18]. The fabric's specifications—including size, yarn composition, weave, ornamentation, color scheme, and design motifs—were thoughtfully chosen to maintain authenticity and cultural significance.

Size-The original dimensions of the Rani Phi textile are 2.4 meters by 1.2 meters. However, for sampling purposes, a reduced size of 1.2 meters by 51 centimeters was used to produce manageable fabric samples for experimentation and evaluation.

Base weave for ornamentation

The base fabric employed a plain weave, offering a straightforward but strong foundation. Ornamentation was added by integrating extra weft designs with rayon yarn, enabling the creation of the intricate motifs and patterns characteristic of Rani Phi.

Colour - The base fabric preserved the traditional authenticity of the Rani Phee by using undyed warp yarns (white) and naturally colored weft yarns (creamy), which imparted an original aesthetic. For ornamentation, the fabric featured red (angangba machu in Manipuri), a traditional color of the Meitei community, enriching the textile's visual appeal.

Design - The border motifs included the iconic traditional Moirang hijan (temple stoops) design along the length, adding depth and texture to the fabric. Additionally, traditional floral motifs known as Namthang Khulat and Kheiroithek Mayek (squirrels motif) adorned the borders, while Kabok Chaibi (rice puff) patterns were distributed throughout the body. In Manipuri, mayek refers to motif

Figure 4: Traditional motifs used

Figure 5: Developed Rani phi

Occasion - The Rani Phi is a traditional upper garment that holds particular importance during marriages and other auspicious events in Manipuri culture, symbolizing tradition, heritage, and the cultural identity of the Meitei community..

Figure 6: Traditional motif used

Figure 7: Developed Muga phanek

Muga Phanek - The traditional garment called Muga phanek was frequently worn by Meitei women on various occasions. Among the different types of Muga phanek textiles, the variant from Khurkhul was especially famous and highly favored. Another important textile, Muga Phanek, served as the lower garment, similar to a sarong. Phanek carried substantial cultural importance for Meitei women and was traditionally made from materials like cotton and silk, particularly mulberry muga silk from Khurkhul.

Size - The original fabric dimensions were 1.7 meters in length and 1.2 meters in width, designed to accommodate various sarong draping styles.

Weave - In the fabric, a plain weave formed the base structure, providing the originality. To add ornamentation, extra weft design motifs were integrated using polyester yarn, which enriched the fabric's visual appeal.

Colour - The fabric's base displayed a captivating contrast: the orange warp yarn introduced vibrancy and warmth, harmonized by the natural color of the weft, creating a visually striking effect. Furthermore, red hues were used for ornamentation i.e. temple stoops border.

Design - The textile's border was embellished with extra weft design motifs, notably featuring the temple stoop pattern, which added intricate detail and texture. In contrast, the body

of the fabric remained free of motifs, creating a clean and versatile look suitable for various occasions.

Festivals/Occasions- Crafted for usefulness, the fabric was ideal for any special occasion, making it suitable for a variety of cultural or ceremonial contexts.

Properties of the constructed textiles

The physical properties of the developed fabrics were rigorously tested following standardized procedures:

Yarn count, Fabric count, cover factor, GSM and Thickness- Yarn count denoted the yarn's thickness, while fabric count specified the number of threads per inch within the fabric. These parameters affected the fabric's weight, thickness, and durability. Muga Phanek had the higher yarn count i.e. Warp- 18's and weft-8's and fabric count i.e. Warp- 39 and weft-32 as it was intended for use as a lower garment, unlike the other fabric for Rani phi- yarn count and Warp-50's & weft-30's and fabric count i.e. Warp-66 & weft-44, which were used as lightweight traditional textile for upper garment.

Table 1: Properties of the developed textiles

Fabric	Cover factor (Kc)	GSM (g/m ²)	Thickness (mm)
Rani phi (Silk/Pineapple)	15.55	56	0.24
Muga Phanek (polyester/pineapple)	17.60	184.4	0.57

The cover factor (Kc) indicated the degree of thread interlacing and coverage within the fabric's structure. The cover factor for both Rani phi and Muga phanek were 15.55 and 17.60 respectively. The Rani phoe exhibited a GSM of 56 g/m² and a thickness of 0.24 mm, signifying a relatively lightweight fabric with moderate thickness. In contrast, Muga Phanek had considerably higher values, with a GSM of 184.4 g/m² and a thickness of 0.57 mm.

ANOVA Analysis - The ANOVA of the cover factor within each textile could not be directly calculated because the cover factor was derived from the mean fabric count, posing a limitation in the analysis. However, a one-way ANOVA (Within variables) was conducted to assess the developed fabrics based on GSM (grams per square meter). For Rani phi, the standard deviation was 1.2 with a standard error of 0.6928. Muga Phanek, on the other hand, had a GSM of 184.4 g/m², with a standard error of 0.1058 and a standard deviation of 0.1833.

Both fabric demonstrated distinct characteristics. Rani phi had a thickness of 0.24 mm with a standard deviation of 0.0303, indicating moderate variability around its average thickness. In contrast, Muga Phanek exhibited a significantly greater thickness of 0.57 mm, with a standard deviation of 0.0239, reflecting relatively higher variability.

Tensile strength - In terms of tensile strength, Rani phoe showed distinct characteristics in its warp and weft directions. The warp direction had a tenacity of 0.20

Kgf/mm, reaching a maximum load of 10.21 Kgf, and experiencing a 19.70% strain at maximum load. Conversely, the weft direction exhibited higher tenacity at 0.30 Kgf/mm, with a maximum load of 14.76 Kgf, and a lower percentage strain of 5.50% at maximum load. In contrast, Muga Phanek demonstrated significant differences in mechanical properties between its warp and weft orientations. The warp direction displayed a tenacity of 0.51 Kgf/mm, achieving a maximum load of 25.52 Kgf and a 48.60% strain at maximum load. On the other hand, the weft direction showed a lower tenacity of 0.45 Kgf/mm, with a maximum load of 22.70 Kgf, and a percentage strain of 5.421% at maximum load. (Table 1.1)

ANOVA (one way) Analysis - For Rani Phee, the mean maximum load in the warp direction was 10.21 kgf, with a standard deviation of 0.36 kgf and a standard error of 0.21 kgf, indicating the average force required to cause failure or deformation when pulled along the warp. In the weft direction, the mean maximum load was 14.76 kgf, with a standard deviation of 1.06 kgf and a standard error of 0.61 kgf.

Table 2 - Tensile properties of the developed textiles

Fabric	Direction	Tenacity (Kgf/mm)	Elongation (mm)	Maximum load (Kgf)	Percentage strain maximum load
Rani phi (Silk/Pineapple)	Warp	0.20	9.85	10.21	19.70
	Weft	0.30	2.75	14.76	5.50
Rani phi (Silk/Pineapple)	Warp	0.51	24.3	25.52	48.60
	weft	0.45	2.71	22.70	5.421

Muga Phanek showed impressive strength characteristics, with a robust mean maximum load of 25.52 kgf in the warp direction, accompanied by a standard deviation of 0.6 kgf and a standard error of 0.35 kgf. In the weft direction, it had a mean maximum load of 22.70 kgf, with a higher standard deviation of 0.96 kgf and a standard error of 0.55 kgf, reflecting substantial strength in both directions.

Stiffness and Drape co-efficient - For Rani phoe stiffness /bending length, the warp dimensions ranged from 3.12 cm (face-to-face) to 3.38 cm (back-to-back), and the weft dimensions varied from 9.68 cm (face-to-face) to 9.32 cm (back-to-back). Muga Phanek had warp dimensions of 2.98 cm (face-to-face) and 2.99 cm (back-to-back), with weft dimensions of 7.9 cm (face-to-face) and 8 cm (back-to-back). To evaluate the feasibility of the developed Rani phi (silk/pineapple) as a substitute for the traditional Rani phi (silk/silk) used by the Meitei community, the drape coefficient of both the developed and original (starched) Rani phi was measured and compared. This comparison is crucial because draping is a key characteristic in wearing Meitei traditional textiles, particularly as a garment draped over the upper body. The drape coefficient of the developed Rani phi fabric, when draped over the disc of drapemeter was measured at 67.57%. In comparison, the original Rani phi fabric (starched) had a lower drape coefficient of 60.61%.

The traditional textiles of the Meitei community were renowned for their inherent stiffness (starch finishing) when draped, a distinctive characteristic. Researchers successfully developed stiff fabrics without the need for additional finishing treatments. In drapability tests, these fabrics showed high drape coefficients, making them suitable for use as upper body drapes. Notably, the obtained drape coefficient values were comparable to those of traditional starched textiles used in Manipur.

Consumer's feedback - The feasibility of using pineapple leaf fiber as an alternative to conventional materials in weaving textiles was confirmed. A survey was conducted to gather feedback from 74 consumers, including weavers aged 18-60 from the Meitei community. The questionnaire included both open-ended and closed-ended questions in English and the local language, Manipuri.

All respondents agreed that fabrics made from pineapple leaf fiber were suitable for use as traditional textiles. 97.3% of participants found pineapple fabrics to resemble silk textiles. Besides local silk, 4% had encountered other fabrics like khadi and tussar silk that resembled pineapple fabrics. Among all respondents 8% disagreed that using only traditional motifs on these fabrics would preserve the authenticity of traditional textiles. Every respondent expressed appreciation for the natural color of pineapple fabrics.

On the likert scale (5-strongly agree, 4- agree, 3-neutral, 2-

disagree and 1- strongly agree), 83.78% of all respondents strongly agreed the use of developed Silk/Pineapple fabric for Rani Phi, while 16.21% agreed with this choice. Similarly, a majority of 90.7% strongly agreed on using developed Fabric Polyester/Pineapple for Muga Phaneak, with the remaining 9.3% expressing 'agree'. In assessing market feasibility, all respondents believed the developed pineapple fabrics would be commercially viable, with 97.3% expressing interest in trying fashion garments made from these fabrics.

4. Conclusion

The integration of pineapple leaf fiber into traditional Meitei textiles provides a sustainable and culturally alternative to conventional materials. These textiles not only meet the aesthetic and functional requirements of traditional attire but also enhance production efficiency by eliminating the need for additional treatments. The positive consumer feedback highlights a market-ready innovation that aligns with traditional practices while fostering sustainability.

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